

EUSAAR – An Unprecedented Network of Aerosol Observation in Europe †

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Abstract – The EUSAAR network (European Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol Research) is a distributed network of 20 high-quality ground-based measurement stations in Europe. Its primary goal is to integrate the measurement of atmospheric aerosol properties and to ensure harmonization, validation, and data diffusion of long-term measurements of particle optical, physical and chemical properties, as these properties constitute the critical parameters for quantifying key processes and the impact of aerosols on climate and air quality. The monitoring network covers a variety of representative environments from clean maritime to polluted continental, including several stations in extreme environments (e.g., arctic, high altitude). The establishment of the research-oriented EUSAAR network has clearly improved the comparability of measurements, best practices in aerosol monitoring procedures, and the availability of high quality aerosol data from the most advanced monitoring stations currently operational in Europe.

Key Words : Aerosol, Air Quality, Monitoring Network.

1. Introduction

Advanced research infrastructures are recognized and have become an essential pillar of atmospheric research in Europe for improving our understanding of atmospheric

processes. The scientific findings over the last decades have highlighted a need for developing a European rather than national approach to advance our knowledge by establishing coordinated research networks for collaboration and information exchange, for providing access to state-of-the-art facilities and advanced measurement techniques. High-quality observations, large-area and long-term monitoring are essential for improving our understanding of atmospheric processes (Laj *et al.*, 2009). To date, the impact of aerosol particles on climate and their relationship to regional air quality is still not fully understood and is associated with large uncertainties. Therefore, coordinated research efforts for monitoring atmospheric aerosols and for investigating climate, environmental and health effects are of fundamental importance for understanding future climate change.

Within Europe, different initiatives have been taken to improve the availability of advanced aerosol-related information through the development of air quality observation networks. These networks comprise advanced research facilities for atmospheric chemistry studies (e.g., EU-

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ROCHAMP: Integration of European Simulation Chambers for Investigating Atmospheric Processes (www.eurochamp.org), policy-oriented in situ measurement networks (e.g., EMEP: European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme for monitoring long-range transport of air pollutants (www.emep.int)) responding to the Geneva convention on long-range transport of pollutants, as well as research-oriented networks such as EARLINET-ASOS: European Aerosol Research Lidar Network (www.earlinet.org) and EUSAAR (European Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol Research (www.eusaar.net)). The EUSAAR network aims at filling the gap in aerosol observations by providing ground-based high-quality data which were previously unavailable to the scientific community.

2. Description of the Network

EUSAAR is an integrated initiative supported by the European Commission with the objective to integrate measurements of atmospheric aerosol properties performed in a distributed network of 20 high-quality European ground-based stations (supersites) geographically distributed over different ecosystem types, to provide advanced data on aerosol properties to a large scientific community and to develop affordable and sustainable solutions to improve monitoring strategies. Prior to the establishment of the network, information on non-regulated* aerosol properties in Europe was only available at selected stations (e.g., Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) stations) and through specific research-based initiatives taken at national or institute levels with limited data availability, leading to a strong heterogeneity of data format and quality. This is considered a major limitation in the current observation system.

The EUSAAR network involves the most advanced monitoring stations currently in operation located in 16 different European countries (cf. **Fig. 1**). These supersites are characterized by a high level of available aerosol instrumentation for measuring physical, chemical, and optical aerosol properties as well as their three-dimensional distribution besides the regulated parameters (e.g., PM_{10}), and show a long record of transnational access and highly relevant long-term monitoring data series. The ground-based research stations have a broad geographical coverage representing specific climates or ecosystems, including four high altitude sites (1,465 – 3,580 m a.s.l.) representative of the background free tropospheric air, low to high

Fig. 1 Distribution of EUSAAR supersites within Europe.

latitude stations ($35 - 78^\circ$ lat.), and stations encountering a variety of air masses from clean maritime to continental polluted within different regional backgrounds (arctic, boreal forest, coastal, rural, urban influence, etc.). An overview of the supersite specifications and additional specific information on the high altitude sites is given in **Tables 1, 2**, respectively.

The networking activities constitute the central core of the network and aim at promoting standardised measurement protocols, harmonizing the monitoring procedures, improving the intercomparability of measurements, ensuring the quality of the measurements, and providing easy access to high quality databases for aerosol properties among the different research sites. All EUSAAR infrastructures participate in regular calibration and intercomparison workshops where each aerosol instrument is quality tested and the infrastructure is evaluated. Those not sufficiently complying with the expected standards undergo modifications and upgrades according to proposed technical recommendations, including advice for best practice in aerosol monitoring and regular training of instrument operators. The infrastructures conforming to the EUSAAR standards are expected to submit their advanced aerosol parameters to the new aerosol observation database EBAS (<http://ebas.nilu.no/>) which has been developed within EUSAAR. The EBAS database is unique and will host the most comprehensive quality-assured aerosol database for state-of-the-art atmospheric modelling.

The network focuses on four essential aerosol parameters which have never been integrated in any coordinated or regulated monitoring programmes in Europe (cf. **Ta-**

* The regulatory standards in EU air quality legislation for particulate matter are mass-based and refer to a size fraction. E.g., PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$ represent the mass concentration of particles with aerodynamic diameters smaller than 10 and 2.5 micrometers, respectively, indicated in $\mu g m^{-3}$.

Table 1 Geographical coordinates of the supersites integrated within EUSAAR

Name of infrastructure		Country	Altitude	Latitude	Longitude
ASP	Aspvreten	Sweden	30 m	58° 48' N	17° 23' E
BEO	BEO Moussala	Bulgaria	2971 m	42° 10' 45" N	23° 35' 07" E
BIR	Birkenes	Norway	190 m	58° 23' N	8° 15' E
CBW	Cabauw	Netherlands	60 m	51° 58' N	4° 55' E
FKL	Finokalia	Greece	250 m	35° 20' N	25° 40' E
HW	Harwell	UK	60 m	51° 34' 17" N	1° 19' 31" W
JFJ	Jungfraujoch	Switzerland	3580 m	46° 32' 53" N	7° 59' 2" E
JRC	JRC-Ispra	Italy	209 m	45° 49' N	08° 38' E
KPO	K-puszta	Hungary	125 m	46° 58' N	19° 33' E
MHD	Mace Head	Ireland	5 m	53° 19' 34" N	9° 53' 14" W
MPZ	Melpitz	Germany	87 m	51° 32' N	12° 54' E
MSY	Montseny	Spain	700 m	41° 46' 51" N	02° 21' 31" E
MTC	Mt. Cimone	Italy	2165 m	44° 11' N	10° 42' E
OBK	Kosetice	Czech Republic	534 m	49° 30' N	15° 05' E
PAL	Pallas	Finland	560 m	67° 58' N	24° 07' E
PDD	Puy de Dôme	France	1465 m	45° 46' N	02° 57' E
PLA	Preila	Lithuania	5 m	55° 55' N	21° 00' E
SMR	Hyytiälä	Finland	181 m	61° 51' N	24° 17' E
VHL	Vavihill	Sweden	172 m	56° 01' N	13° 09' E
ZEP	Zeppelin	Norway	474 m	78° 55' N	11° 54' E

Table 2 Monitoring activities and specific information for the high altitude EUSAAR supersites. Listed are measurements that are either continuous and/or regular or part of major measurement campaigns (* The ZEP station is not at high altitude but included due to its location in an extreme arctic environment)

High altitude station	Basic Environmental Observatory Moussala (BEO)	High Altitude Research Station Jungfraujoch (JFJ)	Mt. Cimone Research Station (MTC)	Puy de Dôme Atmospheric Measurement Site (PDD)	Arctic Zeppelin Station (ZEP)
Altitude (a.s.l.)	2971 m	3580 m	2165 m	1465 m	474 m*
www (incl. online data)	http://beo-db.inrne.bas.bg/moussala/	http://www.ifjungo.ch/	http://www.isac.cnr.it/cimone/	http://www.obs.univ-bpclermont.fr/atmos/pdd/visitepuydedome/accueil.htm	http://tarantula.nilu.no/niluweb/services/zeppelin/
Station access	year-round (dependent on weather conditions), accommodation available, access upon request	year-round, accommodation available, access upon application	year-round (limited in fall-spring), accommodation available, access upon request	year-round, accommodation available, access upon request	year-round, accommodation available, access upon application
Measurements / monitoring activities					
Aerosol physical properties (number size distribution)	x	x	x	x	x
Aerosol optical properties (S: light scattering, A: absorption, D: optical depth)	S	S, A, D	S, A	S, A	S, A, D
Aerosol chemistry (I: inorganic, O: OC/EC)		I, O	I, O	I, O	I
Aerosol hygroscopicity		x		x	
Aerosol 3D (Lidar)				x	x
Bioaerosol				x (in cloud droplets)	
Radioactive aerosol	x	x	x	x	
Reactive gases, ozone, and/or aerosol precursor gases	x	x	x	x	x
Greenhouse gases		x	x	x	x
Heavy metals	x				x
Solar radiation	x	x	x	x	x
Meteorological parameters	x	x	x	x	x
Other	Gamma background cosmic ray (muon and neutron flux)		Radon measurements, lightning detection	PM ₁₀ (TEOM)	

Table 3 Monitoring status of aerosol parameters of interest to air quality and climate studies (EMEP levels are defined as follows: level-1: long-term basic chemical and physical parameters, level-2: additional physical/chemical speciation to assess air pollution and their long-range transport, level-3: research-driven physico-chemical parameters)

Aerosol parameter	Aerosol properties	Monitoring requirements
Inorganic composition	<i>Chemical</i>	EMEP level 1
<i>Organic composition (OC/EC)</i>		<i>EUSAAR</i> (suggested as EMEP level 2)
<i>Number size distribution (dN/dlogD)</i>	<i>Physical</i>	<i>EUSAAR</i> (suggested as EMEP level 3)
PM mass (PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀)		EMEP level 1
<i>Light scattering coefficient</i>	<i>Optical</i>	<i>EUSAAR</i>
<i>Light absorption coefficient</i>		<i>EUSAAR</i>
Aerosol optical depth		PHOTONS/AeroNET, WMO-GAW
Vertical profile		EARLINET-ASOS

Table 4 Instruments and analysis techniques used within EUSAAR

Aerosol parameter	Used instrument (s) / Measurement technique (s)
Organic composition (OC/EC)	Sunset Laboratory Dual-Optical Carbonaceous Analyser with thermal-optical protocols by NIOSH, IMPROVE, variants of and optimized EUSAAR protocol
Number size distribution (dN/dlogD)	Mobility size spectrometer (Differential Mobility Particle Sizer (DMPS), Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS), both commercial and custom-built)
Light scattering coefficient	Integrating nephelometer (TSI model 3563, Radiance Research model M903, Ecotech model 9003)
Light absorption coefficient	Aethalometer Particle Soot Absorption Photometer (PSAP) Multi-Angle Absorption Photometer (MAAP)
Hygroscopicity:	
a. Hygroscopic growth factor	a. Hygroscopicity Tandem Differential Mobility Analyser (HTDMA), custom-built
b. RH-dependent light scattering coefficient	b. Humidified three-wavelength integrating nephelometer (TSI Model 3563), custom-built

bles 3, 4). EUSAAR furthermore develops a new generation of standard humidity-controlled aerosol monitors for long-term monitoring activities. EUSAAR also leads the development of a near real-time data processing system to automate quality-assured transmission of advanced aerosol parameters from the measurement stations to the database as well as a novel cost-effective method for measuring vertical aerosol optical properties using MAX-DOAS technique. Finally, EUSAAR enables and enhances the accessibility of researchers to the advanced aerosol instrumentation at the superstations through the trans-national access activities, and promotes capacity building through frequent aerosol training courses to young scientists and personnel from aerosol measuring stations. EUSAAR involves 21 European partner institutions and is coordinated by the French National Scientific Research Centre (CNRS) in Clermont-Ferrand.

3. Results

During the first three years of EUSAAR, a series of calibration workshops were conducted to characterize the dif-

ferent instruments and methods, to evaluate their intercomparability, and to develop technical standards intended to form a minimum of measurement requirements. The results of the first series of workshops have contributed to developing harmonized measurement and analysis procedures for the methods which are discussed in this section.

3.1 Measurement of Aerosol Physical Parameters

3.1.1 Particle Mobility Size Spectrometers

Custom-made and commercially available particle mobility size spectrometers such as DMPS (Differential Mobility Particle Sizer) and SMPS (Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer) systems have widely been used in the past two decades for conducting long-term and routine measurements of aerosol number size distributions in the submicrometer particle size range. Although this parameter constitutes a key parameter for quantifying the direct and indirect aerosol effect, only few studies have been performed to compare the measured size distributions and performance of these different systems. Several comprehensive intercomparison experiments conducted within the frame of EUSAAR reveal that the various spectrometers

measuring at the same setup under controlled conditions differ strongly with uncertainties of up to 25 % in both determination of size and number concentration due to technical design and the inversion routines used. Therefore, a harmonized technical standard and data structure for mobility size spectrometers has been developed within EUSAAR with respect to instrumental set-up, measurement mode, data evaluation, and quality control. These recommendations aim at improving the data accuracy, comparability, and traceability of measured particle number size distributions, particularly important for real-time conditions and long-term operation where the system parameters are only routinely checked (Wiedensohler *et al.*, 2009).

3.1.2 Hygroscopic Tandem Differential Mobility Analyzer

Hygroscopic Tandem Differential Mobility Analyzers (HTDMAs) are used worldwide in laboratory experiments and field campaigns to measure the water uptake of aerosol particles as a function of relative humidity. As the size-dependent hygroscopic growth factor influences the light scattering by particles, their potential to act as cloud condensation nuclei, and their chemical reactivity, the results of HTDMA measurements are important for estimating the aerosol direct climate forcing. Within EUSAAR, several intercomparison workshops with custom-built instruments used in Europe have been conducted to calibrate the instruments, validate their performance and accuracy, and identify the causes of measurement discrepancies. Based on the workshop results, recommendations are given to improve existing or to build new HTDMAs with respect to their design, standardised calibration, instrument validation, field operation, and data analysis procedures (Duplissy *et al.*, 2008; Gysel *et al.*, 2009). This will contribute to ensuring the quality of data and comparability of field measurements.

3.2 Measurement of Aerosol Optical Parameters

3.2.1 Integrating Nephelometer

The integrating nephelometer measures the light scattering coefficient of aerosol particles which constitutes the key property of every radiative transfer and climate model and is, therefore, in wide use for monitoring and research applications related to air pollution and climate. The commercially available nephelometers from various manufacturers differ in the size of their measurement volume, their optical geometry, and their wavelengths. These parameters affect the detection limit and the performance of the nephelometer. Within EUSAAR, several units of the three most widely used models were characterized with respect to their calibration accuracy, stability and non-idealities of their angular illumination function. As a result of the workshop,

improved correction mechanisms were proposed to account for the non-ideal illumination due to truncation of the sensing volumes in the near-forward and near-backward angular ranges and for non-Lambertian illumination from the light sources, particularly for two models that have never been intercompared prior to EUSAAR, and recommendations for operational data analysis were presented (Müller *et al.*, 2008). Establishing standard procedures for routine measurements of optical parameters are fundamental for a sustainable and reliable observation network for aerosol optical data across Europe.

3.2.2 Humidified Nephelometer

Data of scattering enhancement by relative humidity is still scarce but important to better characterize aerosol optical properties at ambient RH, and, thus, to help reduce the large uncertainties in the direct climate forcing by aerosol particles. Within EUSAAR, a new humidified nephelometer was developed to measure the hygroscopic aerosol behaviour (Schmidhauser *et al.*, 2008). This new generation of humidity-controlled aerosol monitor is intended for long-term measurement applications and will serve as a standard for future intercomparison exercises.

3.3 Measurement of the Aerosol Carbonaceous Fraction

Carbonaceous material represents an important component in atmospheric aerosol particles and is known to have major impacts on aerosol radiative forcing and human health. A variety of different thermal and thermal-optical measurement techniques have been developed in the past to discriminate between the organic (OC) and elemental (EC) carbon fraction, leading to substantially different results and implying that data from different laboratories at various sites are most likely not comparable and affected by unknown errors. As there is currently no standard procedure for determining carbonaceous aerosol fraction in Europe, a comprehensive work has been carried out within EUSAAR to investigate the causes of differences in the EC measured using different thermal evolution protocols and to assess and mitigate major positive and negative biases affecting thermal-optical analysis (Cavalli *et al.*, 2009). A EUSAAR standardized thermal-optical protocol now contributes to improving and harmonizing the data quality of the different types of carbonaceous particulate matter encountered across Europe. The protocol is being discussed in the frame of the European Center for Normalization as part of standardization procedures for aerosol characterization in Europe.

4. Conclusions and Outlook

EUSAAR has established a unique network of research

infrastructures in Europe for integrating and harmonizing measurements of aerosol properties and for diffusing high quality aerosol products to the scientific community. The network includes 20 of the most advanced ground-based aerosol measurement stations in Europe. Results from comprehensive instrument intercomparison workshops indicate a strong need to develop best practices and technical standards in aerosol monitoring to improve the quality of long-term measurements and the comparability between the different observation and research sites. The centralised online EUSAAR database, containing comprehensive, concise and accessible aerosol information, offers an unparalleled and precious tool for modellers to validate and improve their regional and global air quality and climate models. With an increasing number of measurement stations and institutions involved in measuring physical, optical, and chemical aerosol parameters, EUSAAR will strive to continue its efforts and consolidate its role for defining the aerosol monitoring strategies to reinforce the basis of atmospheric research in Europe.

Since its establishment in 2006, the EUSAAR aerosol observation network has constantly grown, having more than 30 associated partners worldwide. All scientists interested in exchanging information and expertise in aerosol observation for mutual benefits are encouraged to participate in the EUSAAR activities by joining the network (www.eusaar.net).

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要旨 – European Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol Research (EUSAAR) ネットワークは、欧州域内 20 箇所に設置された高精度な地上型観測ステーションを結ぶ、分散型ネットワークである。EUSAAR ネットワークの主要目標は、大気エアロゾルの性質の測定を集約し、粒子の光学的、物理的、化学的特性に関する長期測定につき、確実に調整、検証し、さらにデータを配布することにある。これらの特性は、エアロゾルが気候や大気質に及ぼす影響や主要プロセスを定量化する際に、重要なパラメータを構成するものである。このモニタリングネットワークは、清浄な海洋から汚染された大陸内部に至るまで、多種多様な代表的環境を網羅しており、極限環境下（たとえば、北極、高所）のステーションもいくつか含んでいる。研究指向型の EUSAAR ネットワークを構築したことにより、測定の比較可能性やエアロゾル・モニタリング手法における最良の方法、および欧州域内で現在稼動している最も進んだモニタリング・ステーションから得られる高精度なエアロゾルデータの利用可能性は、明らかに向上したと言える。

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